

```

Query 5637 ACGAGTGCACATCCCCATCGGCGCTGGAATCTGCGCCAGCTACCAGACACAGACAAAGA 5696
          |||
Sbjct 2623 ACGAGTGCACATCCCCATCGGCGCCGGCATCTGTGCCAGCTACCAGACCCAGACCAAGT 2564
Query 5697 GCCACCGGAGAGCCAGAAGCGTGGCCAGCCAGAGCATCATTGCCTACACAATGTCTCTGG 5756
          |||
Sbjct 2563 CACACCGGAGGGCAAGGAGCGTGGCCAGCCAGAGCATCATCGCCTACACCATGAGCCTGG 2504
Query 5757 GCGCCGAGAACAGCGTGGCCTACTCCAACAACCTCTATCGCTATCCCCACCAACTTCACCA 5816
          |||
Sbjct 2503 GCGCCGAGAACAGCGTGGCCTACAGCAACAACAGCATCGCCATCCCCACCAACTTCACCA 2444
Query 5817 TCAGCGTGACCACAGAGATCCTGCCTGTGTCCATGACCAAGACCAGCGTGGACTGCACCA 5876
          |||
Sbjct 2443 TCAGCGTGACCACCGAGATTCTGCCCGTGAGCATGACCAAGACCAGCGTGGACTGCACCA 2384
Query 5877 TGTACATCTGCGGCGATTCCACCGAGTGCTCCAACCTGCTGCTGCAGTACGGCAGCTTCT 5936
          |||
Sbjct 2383 TGTACATCTGCGGCGACAGCACCGAGTGCAGCAACCTGCTGCTGCAGTACGGCAGCTTCT 2324
Query 5937 GCACCCAGCTGAAAAGAGCCCTGACAGGGATCGCCGTGGAACAGGACAAGAACACCCAAG 5996
          |||
Sbjct 2323 GCACCCAGCTGAACCGGGCCCTGACCGGCATCGCCGTGGAGCAGGACAAGAACACCCAGC 2264
Query 5997 AGGTGTTGCCCCAAGTGAAGCAGATCTACAAGACCCCTCCTATCAAGTACTTCGGCGGCT 6056
          |||
Sbjct 2263 AGGTGTTGCCCCAGGTGAAGCAGATCTACAAGACCCCTCCCATCAAGTACTTCGGCGGCT 2204
Query 6057 TCAATTTAGCCAGATTCTGCCCGATCCTAGCAAGCCCAGCAAGCGGAGCTTCATCGAGG 6116
          |||
Sbjct 2203 TCAACTTCAGCCAGATCCTGCCCGACCCAGCAAGCCCAGCAAGCGGAGCTTCATCGAGG 2144
Query 6117 ACCTGCTGTTCAACAAAGTGACACTGGCCGACGCCGGCTTCATCAAGCAGTATGGCGATT 6176
          |||
Sbjct 2143 ACCTGCTGTTCAACAAAGGTGACCCTAGCCGACGCCGGCTTCATCAAGCAGTACGGCGACT 2084

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Fig. 1. BLASTn result indicating 91% overall identity (3615 / 3972) between Pfizer bivalent expression vector BNT162b2 (GenBank: OR134577.1) and ModeRNA mRNA1273 expression vector (OR134578.1) with respect to the 20 bp fragment (marked red) found integrated within chromosome 19 (chr19:55,482,637–55,482,674, GRCh38), cytoband 19q13.42 of a patient developing stage IV bladder cancer as published by Catanzaro *et al.* 2025. Full alignment between both vectors is available in [Supplementary Data - S2](#).